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URBAN-WASTE

Urban strategies for Waste Management in Tourist Cities

D3.7 – Policy briefs draft

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Abstract

This deliverable contains two policy briefs that summarize the URBAN-WASTE experience in mobilizing stakeholders in the co-creation, co-implementation and co-monitoring of eco-innovative waste management and prevention strategies, describing the methodology applied, results achieved, lessons learnt and a set of policy recommendations for further mobilization.

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List of abbreviations

CE	Consulta Europa
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
CoP	Communities of Practices
MMLP	Mobilization and Mutual Learning Plan
EU	The European Union
EC	European Commission
EASME	European Agency for Small and Medium Enterprises

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POLICY BRIEF May 2019

Mobilizing stakeholders for improved waste management and prevention strategies in touristic cities: the URBAN-WASTE experience

Executive summary

With increasing numbers in tourism in many EU cities, effective policies are needed in order to better manage and reduce waste generation. However, these policies must not be drawn by solely regional and local authorities but also by all the different actors that affect and are affected by it, which include local authorities, municipal services and companies in charge of the waste collection and treatment, tourism service providers, research institutes, citizens, tourists and many more. Thus, among other benefits, mobilizing stakeholders to build on a participatory approach will ensure that the decision-making process is transparent and legitimate.

In this context, the URBAN-WASTE project proposes a method for effective and inclusive participation of different stakeholders for the co-designing, co-implementation and co-monitoring of waste management and prevention strategies that set the basis for local and regional collaborative policy making.

It does so through the implementation of a mobilization strategy, and more specifically through the creation of the so-called Communities of Practice in 11 EU cities and regions.

In total, more than 500 stakeholders participated on the communities, where they collaborated hand-in-hand with local municipalities and other authorities. However, although the experience has been proved successful, the path has not been exempting from obstacles and challenges to overcome. But the methodology applied, results achieved, and the take-away lessons learnt provide a framework for potential replicability from other EU decision makers shaping waste policies.

A set of policy recommendations is provided with aims at encouraging policy makers to follow collaborative and participatory approaches where all relevant stakeholders are mobilized to be part of the drafting of strategies towards more sustainable cities.

Background

The URBAN-WASTE project, under the H2020 funding programme, aims at developing eco-innovative and gender-sensitive waste prevention and management strategies in cities characterized by high levels of tourism in order to reduce the urban waste production and improve municipal waste management. These strategies are intended to facilitate the reintroduction of waste as a resource into the urban metabolism flows and to address waste management, risk prevention and land-use as an integral part of urban development.

In comparison with other cities, tourist cities face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flows and the specificity of tourism industry and of tourists as waste producers. These challenges threaten the preservation and conservation of those ecosystem services offered by tourist destinations, which are at the basis of the socio-economic survival of tourist cities and of their attractiveness. URBAN-WASTE aims at preserving the ecosystems from degradation caused by irresponsible waste management.

Thus, the general objective of the project is to reduce waste production, increase waste recycling

and improve municipal waste management in tourist cities through the implementation of urban eco-innovative strategies for waste prevention and management. More specifically, the project's objectives are to:

- apply and integrate urban metabolic approach for waste urban policies;
- address gender in waste prevention and management.
- foster and structure a stakeholder participatory framework for policy-making in waste management;

In order to build such successful stakeholder participatory framework, 11 pilot cities and regions, namely Copenhagen, Dubrovnik-Neretva, Tuscany Region, Kavala, Nice, Lisbon, Ponta Delgada, Nicosia, Syracuse, Tenerife and Santander activated, engaged and opened a dialogue with a wide range of stakeholders with aims at co-designing, co-implementing and co-monitoring the eco-innovative waste prevention and management strategies. As a result, total of 22 strategies or measures were developed and piloted within the project.

More information at <http://www.urban-waste.eu/>

Methodology

The starting point requires to understand and value the importance of involving a wide and rich number of stakeholders into the process of developing urban and waste management policies, it is key to highlight the main benefits and outcomes that this brings (Reed *et al*, 2000; Kleivink *et al*, 2012):

- quality and durability of decisions is greater
- social consensus is more easily reached
- the process of decision-making and final decisions becomes more transparent and legitimate.

In this way, the URBAN-WASTE mobilization strategy is built around the concept of the

Communities of Practice (CoPs), which can be defined as groups of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interaction and on an on-going basis. These groups of people would occasionally meet to learn from each other and are characterized by three key dimensions: mutual engagement, joint enterprise and shared repertoire (Wenger et al. 2002).

In the strict sense of the concept, these groups would be formed spontaneously. Nevertheless, in URBAN-WASTE these communities have been triggered and driven by a Mobilization and Mutual Learning Plan (De Luca *et al*, 2017) with aims at both gathering inputs from stakeholders for the generation of the waste prevention and management strategies and creating the basis for a successful implementation and monitoring of progress.

The Mobilization and Mutual Learning Plan provided a framework for an effective identification of relevant stakeholders that are directly or indirectly affected by local waste management and urban planning policies. In addition, the plan envisaged the establishment of one CoP in each of the pilot cases, where participants would interact through dedicated face-to-face events and through an electronic platform.

Thus, five CoP events were organized whereas each of them comprised a series of specific objectives that would ensure an effective and coherent process towards reaching the general objectives, which were to:

In order to assess the effectiveness of the CoPs, a monitoring system was put in place, which was constituted by a set of quantitative indicators such as the number of participants, of measures proposed, of measures selected or of partnerships signed, among others, and qualitative indicators such as the type of stakeholders engaged, sense of belonging and of influence in the CoPs, etc.

Moreover, and running in parallel with the Mutual Learning and Mobilization Plan, a Gender Strategy was embedded with aims at mainstreaming gender balance and other aspects into the mobilization process. It involved an initial baseline analysis on local authorities and stakeholder's gender balance, focus groups to understand and highlight gender

differences in waste management practices and raise awareness, dedicated face-to-face and online trainings, an analysis of the gender impact on measures and a final evaluation of changes experienced in the pilot cases.

Results

The mobilization strategy applied in URBAN-WASTE proved that a more transparent process into decision-making can be achieved. Knowledge, experiences and other inputs from an extensive variety of stakeholders were collected and, together with the local authorities, between 3 and 6 strategies for improved waste prevention and management were designed, selected, implemented and monitored.

restaurants associations, citizens and civil society organizations, universities and research institutions, airports, port authorities, circular economy associations, environmental agencies, and many more. Maintaining an active participation of stakeholders in the communities was vital for achieving enough representativeness from all groups (*Figure 1*).

Considering all 11 cities and regions, more than 500 stakeholders were involved in the CoPs. From the beginning, representativeness of key groups of stakeholders dealing with, affected by or producing waste was seek and achieved, counting on the active participation of local administrations and authorities, waste management services/companies, tourism associations and offices, accommodation providers, hotels and

In this sense, the climax of this participatory process was reached with the signing of voluntary partnerships between the municipalities and the different stakeholders committed to implement the eco-innovative strategies, which accounted for more than 150 partnerships. Moreover, a strong communication strategy during and after the implementation attracted and engaged additional stakeholders.

Figure 1. Stakeholder participation in CoP events

Although the mobilization strategy had, overall, the same results in all pilot cities and regions, the experience was different in each of them and thus the type of events varied according to the local needs and specificities in form of workshops, roundtables, working groups, etc. Synergies with

local events were promoted in order to enhance the reach-out effect. The co-development of strategies culminated with a list of 22 strategies or measures from which local authorities and stakeholders would decide on implementing at least 2 or 3 of them in each city or region (*Table I*).

Measure	Description
1	Doggy bags
2	Food waste prevention at buffets and restaurants
3	On-site composting in tourist establishments
4	Collection points for used cooking oil
5	Selective collection of biowaste from hotels and restaurants
6	Partnerships between hotels and charities for reuse initiatives
7	Substitution of disposable products in hotels
8	Reuse initiative in camping sites
9	Communication campaign in reuse through swap markets
10	Waste sorting in hotel rooms
11	Recycling advisors for tourist establishments
12	Sorting bins in public and touristic places
13	Promotion of tap water
14	Waste sorting instructions translated
15	Waste sorting in marinas
16	Information on waste sorting for cruise ships
17	Pocket boxes and ashtrays against litter
18	Eco-events guidelines
19	Awareness campaign on marine litter
20	Food tracking device
21	WasteApp
22	Food donation from restaurants and hotels to charities

Table I. URBAN-WASTE measures list

The number of measures selected, implemented and monitored as well as the type of stakeholders involved in each city or region is detailed below.

Copenhagen

Strategies: 4

Stakeholders in CoP: tourism organizations, Technical and Environmental Administration, hotels, municipal street sweepers, local environmental community, citizens, etc.

Dubrovnik

Strategies: 4

Stakeholders in CoP: Regional and local authorities, tourism boards, waste management workers, tourism workers, NGOs, museums, high schools, etc.

Florence

Strategies: 6

Stakeholders in CoP: Tourism technical institute, food banks, environmental agencies, hotel representatives, NGOs, waste and water management companies, tourists, etc.

CoP in Florence

Kavala

Strategies: 5

Stakeholders in CoP: local authorities, hotels, NGOs, citizens, Public Benefit Organization, restaurant associations, Waste Management Department, Environment Departments, Chamber of Commerce, airport, port, etc.

Lisbon

Strategies: 5

Stakeholders in CoP: Hotels and restaurants associations, Tourism office, NGOs, food suppliers, Circular Economy association, tourists, citizens, Public space and waste management department, etc.

Nice

Strategies: 5

Stakeholders in CoP: Tourism Office, municipalities, restaurants, hotels, SMEs, harbors, Waste management department, local politicians, citizens, etc.

Nicosia

Strategies: 4

Stakeholders in CoP: Hotels and restaurants, Public Health and Hygiene department, Union of Cyprus Municipalities, Cyprus Sustainable Tourism Initiative, Tourism Organization, Department of Environment, Collective Compliance System for

Packaging and Packaging Waste, Marine Environment Protection Association, SMEs, consulting companies, tourists, citizens, etc.

Ponta Delgada

Strategies: 4

Stakeholders in CoP: waste management authorities, local authorities, transport providers, hotel accommodation service, food and beverage services, tourists, citizens, SMEs, etc.

Santander

Strategies: 6

Stakeholders in CoP: Waste Management authorities, hotels and accommodation services, Tourist/Events Organization, Municipal Service provider/Waste Management, citizens, tourists, etc.

Syracuse

Strategies: 4

Stakeholders in CoP: local authorities, citizens, Waste Management authorities, hand craft association, Tourist association, schools, hotel association, restaurants., etc.

Tenerife

Strategies: 6

Stakeholders in CoP: representatives of tourism industry, research organizations, Waste management companies, environmental non-profit organizations, civil society organization, tourists, hotels, municipal service provider, NGO's, citizens, etc.

CoP in Tenerife

Challenges and lessons learnt

The participatory process applied in the project and its evaluation has showcased a series of obstacles and successes along the way from which other EU cities facing high tourism pressures and seeking to open a constructive dialogue where stakeholders are empowered in decision making could benefit.

It was observed that the approach to engage stakeholders is affected by many factors, among which, cultural contexts are important to consider. Certain practices were appropriate for a particular city or region while it would be considered ineffective in others. Therefore, although a common plan is needed, local specificities must be taken into account when applying tailored approaches. Likewise, willingness to collaborate is the first and elementary ingredient in this process. In some cities or regions this was more evident than in others where initial engagement required more time and efforts.

Drafting Public-Private Partnerships helped to settle the commitment of stakeholders and ensured continuity to the implementation of the strategies. These helped to clearly define roles and responsibilities of each party, timeline of actions,

CoP in Lisbon

operational steps, monitoring indicators, and resources needed beforehand.

Another key aspect identified was the need of disseminating effectively the CoPs in order to not only convey as many stakeholders as possible but also to ensure representativeness of relevant ones. Continuous communication with all stakeholders will keep them well informed, interested and actively engaged. In the same line, stakeholders must have a very clear idea on their role within the CoP and why is their contribution valuable.

Furthermore, although a high degree of flexibility on the format of the CoP events should be granted to the organizers and participants, a master plan with clear objectives for each session are essential to guarantee that the overall purpose of is being fulfilled.

All in all, the mobilization approach applied to URBAN-WASTE proved to be successful and satisfactory to achieve more transparent, legitimate decision making, and contributed to build trust among local authorities and stakeholders.

CoP in Santander

Policy recommendations

- Waste management and prevention as well as sustainability policies should be developed with the active participation of all those actors that affect and are affected by it. Otherwise, the implications of the policies might fail to address all needs and might as well cause the opposite effect as intended.
- An effective channel of participation should be fostered, where stakeholders can work together towards a common goal.
- Measures to ensure that participant's inputs are taken into account and where the co-development of the policies is evident should be set up. The participatory approach should go further than the traditional stakeholder consultation.
- Local specificities should be considered as to find the most appropriate and cost-effective channel for collaboration, as of being on a face-to-face format (workshops, roundtables, etc.) or remote (online platform, telephone, etc.)
- Building up on a concept (community of practice, lab, hub, etc.) that stakeholders can relate to, feel identified and nurture their sense of belonging can motivate engagement.
- Identifying and engaging stakeholders requires to communicate efficiently the importance of their contributions and their role within the participatory process.
- Furthermore, ensuring representativeness from relevant stakeholders that should be present when drafting waste management policies is key. However, equally important is to cultivate an inclusive method in terms of gender, age, educational level, etc. to acquire a rich mix of representatives.
- Adequate financial, human and technical resources should be invested and allocated into the participatory method in order to ensure that the mobilization is impactful and effective.
- Feedback collection and co-development of policies should be done at an early stage of policy making so that there is enough time to allow a greater range of ideas incorporated into the policies.
- Exchanging and disseminating the results and lessons learnt from a participatory approach in waste management and prevention policies at local and regional levels could allow for the upscaling to national or European level as well.

Resources

De Luca, C., Perello, M., Bel, J.B., Kovács, E., Kazeroni, M., Medieu, A., Bolognani, O., 2017, URBAN-WASTE - D3.4 URBAN-WASTE Mobilization and Mutual Learning Plan

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Reed M.S., Dougill A.J., Baker T., Participatory indicator development: what can ecologists and local communities learn from each other?, Ecological Applications, 2012, 18, pp. 1253-1269

Wenger E., McDermott R. A., Snyder W., Cultivating Communities of Practice: A Guide to Managing Knowledge, 2002, Harward business School Press., Boston

POLICY BRIEF May 2018

Stakeholder involvement in collaborative formulation and implementation of waste management and prevention strategies: the URBAN-WASTE case

Executive summary

With increasing numbers in tourism in many EU cities, effective policies are needed in order to better manage and reduce waste generation. However, these policies must not be drawn by solely regional and local authorities but also by all the different actors that affect and are affected by it, which include local authorities, municipal services and companies in charge of the waste collection and treatment, tourism service providers, research institutes, citizens, tourists and many more. Thus, among other benefits, mobilizing stakeholders to build on a participatory approach will ensure that the decision-making process is transparent and legitimate.

In this context, the URBAN-WASTE project proposes a method for effective and inclusive participation of different stakeholders for the co-designing, co-implementation and co-monitoring of waste management and prevention strategies that set the basis for local and regional collaborative policy making.

It does so through the implementation of a mobilization strategy, and more specifically through the creation of the so-called Communities of Practice in 11 EU cities and regions.

As the project continues with its implementation, up to date the stakeholder participation in the communities of practice has been successful and active, reaching an estimated number of over 400 stakeholders working together with municipalities and other local authorities to draw strategies that could shape the future of waste policies.

The URBAN-WASTE approach seeks to serve as an example for urban planners and other policy makers in applying an effective participatory methodology that could be replicated in other EU cities.

Background

The URBAN-WASTE project, under the H2020 funding programme, aims at developing eco-innovative and gender-sensitive waste prevention and management strategies in cities characterized by high levels of tourism in order to reduce the urban waste production and improve municipal waste management. These strategies are intended to facilitate the reintroduction of waste as a resource into the urban metabolism flows and to address waste management, risk prevention and land-use as an integral part of urban development.

In comparison with other cities, tourist cities face additional challenges related to waste prevention and management due to their geographical and climatic conditions, the seasonality of tourism flows and the specificity of tourism industry and of tourists as waste producers. These challenges threaten the preservation and conservation of those ecosystem services offered by tourist destinations, which are at the basis of the socio-economic survival of tourist cities and of their attractiveness. URBAN-WASTE aims at preserving the ecosystems from degradation caused by irresponsible waste management.

Thus, the general objective of the project is to reduce waste production, increase waste recycling and improve municipal waste management in tourist cities through the implementation of urban eco-innovative strategies for waste prevention and management. More specifically, the project's objectives are to:

- apply and integrate urban metabolic approach for waste urban policies;
- address gender in waste prevention and management.
- foster and structure a stakeholder participatory framework for policy-making in waste management;

In order to build such successful stakeholder participatory framework, 11 pilot cities and regions, namely Copenhagen, Dubrovnik-Neretva, Tuscany Region, Kavala, Nice, Lisbon, Ponta Delgada, Nicosia, Syracuse, Tenerife and Santander activated, engaged and opened a dialogue with a wide range of stakeholders with aims at co-designing, co-implementing and co-monitoring the eco-innovative waste prevention and management strategies. As a result, total of 22 strategies or measures have been developed and each of the pilot cities and regions will implement a selection of them in the coming months.

More information at <http://www.urban-waste.eu/>

Methodology

The URBAN-WASTE mobilization strategy is built around the concept of the Communities of Practice (CoPs), which can be defined as groups of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interaction and on an on-going basis. These groups of people would occasionally meet to learn from each other and are characterized by three key dimensions: mutual engagement, joint enterprise and shared repertoire (Wenger et al. 2002).

In the strict sense of the concept, these groups would be formed spontaneously. Nevertheless, in URBAN-WASTE these communities have been triggered and driven by a Mobilization and Mutual Learning Plan (De Luca *et al*, 2017) with aims at both gathering inputs from stakeholders for the generation of the waste prevention and management strategies and creating the basis for a successful implementation and monitoring.

The Mobilization and Mutual Learning Plan provides a framework for an effective identification of relevant stakeholders that are directly or indirectly affected by local waste management and urban planning policies. In addition, the plan envisages the establishment of one CoP in each of the pilot cases, where participants would interact through dedicated face-to-face events and through an electronic platform.

Thus, four CoP events were organized whereas each of them comprised a series of specific objectives that would ensure an effective and coherent process towards reaching the general objectives:

- **1st CoP event** → Recruit additional stakeholders as members of the CoPs, present the project, inform about EU targets on waste management and present specific local challenges and objectives.
- **2nd CoP event** → Collect inputs and proposals from participants for the generation of strategies.
- **3rd CoP event** → Select at least 2-3 strategies to be implemented locally.
- **4th CoP event** → Present to a wider public the strategies selected, sign Public-Private Partnerships and publicly launch the implementation phase.

Moreover, a monitoring system has been applied to assess the effectiveness of the CoPs. This system involves a set of quantitative indicators such as the number of participants, of measures proposed, of measures selected or of partnerships signed, among others, and qualitative indicators such as the type of stakeholders engaged, sense of belonging and of influence in the CoPs, etc.

Achievements

Even though the project is ongoing, and up to date 3 out of the 4 CoP events have taken place, positive results have been achieved so far. A wide range of stakeholders have been mobilized within each of the 11 pilot cities and regions to develop a list of 22 measures, with support from the technical partners from the project, from which a selection of between 3 and 6 will be implemented in the coming months, after the signing of the Public-Private Partnerships. This will imply the official launch of the implementation phase of those strategies.

Although in general the type of stakeholders engaged corresponds to similar groups in every city or region, this varies slightly from one to another, and actors such as waste management services/companies, tourism associations and offices, accommodation providers, hotels and restaurants associations, citizens and civil society organizations, universities and research institutions, airports, port authorities, circular economy associations, environmental agencies and other local authorities have been involved from the beginning. Up to date, more than 400 stakeholders have participated in the CoPs.

The type of events would vary depending on each local specificity or what was considered most effective in each city or region. Hence, these would take different formats such as workshops, roundtables, etc. However, these would vary as well depending on the objective of each event. For example, the 1st CoP main objective

was to attract and engage as many stakeholders into the communities as possible, and therefore synergies with relevant local events where a lot of participation was expected were encouraged.

1st CoP in Florence

1st CoP in Ponta Delgada

The 2nd CoP already allowed ideas generation and collection of inputs from stakeholders in terms of potential waste management and prevention strategies that could be set up locally. This culminated with the generation of a list of 22 measures from where they will make a final selection during the following CoP event. The co-developed measures are:

- Doggy bags
- Food waste prevention at buffets and restaurants
- On-site composting in tourist establishments
- Collection points for used cooking oil
- Selective collection of biowaste from hotels and restaurants
- Partnerships between hotels and charities for reuse initiatives
- Substitution of disposable products in hotels
- Reuse initiative in camping sites
- Communication campaign in reuse through swap markets
- Waste sorting in hotel rooms
- Recycling advisors for tourist establishments
- Sorting bins in public and touristic places
- Promotion of tap water
- Waste sorting instructions translated
- Waste sorting in marinas
- Information on waste sorting for cruise ships
- Pocket boxes and ashtrays against litter
- Eco-events guidelines
- Awareness campaign on marine litter
- Food tracking device
- WasteApp
- Food donation from restaurants and hotels to charities

During the 3rd CoP where the measures to implement were selected, stakeholders and municipalities also started drafting together what would be the operative plan for the effective implementation. This operative plan defines the roles and responsibilities of the actors involved in each measure, the operational steps, timing,

resources needed and available and monitoring indicators. The 4th CoP will serve as an occasion to finalize those plans and officially sign the Public-Private Partnerships and engage further stakeholders. For this, strong efforts are invested in disseminating and attracting additional actors not only during but also before and after CoP events.

Challenges

Despite having a mobilization strategy that draws the participatory process, there are many factors and local specificities that should be taken into account. For example, certain practices were appropriate for a particular city or region while it would be considered ineffective in others. Moreover, some municipalities were more familiarized with collaborative and participatory practices than others, and engagement of stakeholders for them required less efforts and time.

In addition, disseminating effectively the CoPs in order to gather as many stakeholders as possible and to ensure representativeness of relevant ones. Continuous communication with all stakeholders will keep them well informed, interested and actively engaged.

Furthermore, although a high degree of flexibility on the format of the CoP events should be granted to the organizers and participants, a master plan with clear objectives for each session are essential to guarantee that the overall purpose of is being fulfilled.

When organizing the CoP events, it is important to count on the necessary skills to efficiently facilitate the sessions and maximize the outcome of the co-creation. Likewise, an effective method for feedback collection should be in place in order account for all participant's inputs.

So far, the implementation of the mobilization strategy applied to URBAN-WASTE, although encountering certain obstacles, has been considered successful and seeks for its replicability in other contexts of policy making.

Policy recommendations

- Waste management and prevention as well as sustainability policies should be developed with the active participation of all those actors that affect and are affected by it.
- Communities of practice are an effective channel for participation of stakeholders in a policy making process. It builds trust between local authorities and other stakeholders whose feedback would otherwise be ignored, it makes the process more transparent and decisions more legitimate.
- The participatory approach should go further than the traditional stakeholder consultation.
- Local specificities should be considered as to find the most appropriate and cost-effective channel for collaboration, as of being on a face-to-face format (workshops, roundtables, etc.) or remote (online platform, telephone, etc.)
- Representativeness from relevant stakeholders should be seek in order to have feedbacks from a wide range of backgrounds.

- Stakeholders should have a clear idea of their role in the participatory process and the importance of their contributions.

Resources

De Luca, C., Perello, M., Bel, J.B., Kovács, E., Kazeroni, M., Medieu, A., Bolognani, O., 2017, URBAN-WASTE - D3.4 URBAN-WASTE Mobilization and Mutual Learning Plan

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